

Wellcome Sanger Institute

Embedding equity in international research collaboration

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Executive Summary

International collaboration is central to the Wellcome Sanger Institute’s mission to ‘apply and explore genomic technologies at scale to advance understanding of biology and improve health’. A significant portion of Sanger’s research is performed in collaboration with partners based in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), and it is a priority for the Institute to ensure that principles of mutual benefit and equity are embedded in these partnerships as it works towards a culture of research excellence.

When working with partners based in LMICs, it is essential that consideration is given to power dynamics to ensure that Sanger research teams do not inadvertently exploit power imbalances through the practice of inequitable research that does not seek meaningful input from, or bring benefit to, local researchers and communities. Not only would this approach be exploitative, but if local partners are not meaningfully involved in the research, then critical skills and perspectives are overlooked – limiting problem-solving power and likely lowering the quality of research outputs – and outputs may be misaligned with local priorities. Therefore, it is both an ethical and scientific imperative that Sanger research teams collaborate closely with partners in an equitable manner.

This report seeks to support Sanger research teams to do this through two sections:

1. A working definition of an equitable collaboration

A working definition of an equitable collaboration has been developed: ‘a **mutually advantageous partnership built on trust, where all partners are intellectual contributors to the project who work together to ensure that tasks and rewards are shared in a fair manner that addresses inequalities**’.

2. Guidelines for Sanger research teams to collaborate equitably with partners based in LMICs

General principles are proposed that guide Sanger research teams in building fair and effective collaborations with partners based in LMICs. These guidelines suggest ways to embed equity throughout all stages of the research collaboration, from partnership building through research design and execution to result dissemination.

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1. Introduction

1.1 International collaboration

International collaboration is central to the Wellcome Sanger Institute's mission to **'apply and explore genomic technologies at scale to advance understanding of biology and improve health'**. Collaborative research enables efficient use of resources for high-quality research, facilitates exchange of expertise and perspectives, and improves mobility for Sanger researchers and international partners. Critically, international research collaborations are essential in understanding and addressing global challenges such as international health disparities, pathogen spread and evolution, and global biodiversity loss.

These challenges can only be effectively tackled when partners from different global settings are empowered to work together as equals and thus feel comfortable to openly share their knowledge, skills, resources and data.

The Sanger Institute collaborates through large international consortia comprising multiple partners from many countries around the world (e.g. Earth BioGenome Project, MalariaGEN, Global Pneumococcal Sequencing Project, Human Cell Atlas, Mutographs, International Common Disease Alliance, Atlas of Variant Effects), as well as through smaller scale one-to-one arrangements between research teams. The Institute also strengthens its collaborative links through its International Fellowship Program¹ and MPhil in Genomic Science². A significant portion of Sanger's research is carried out in collaboration with partners based in Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs), and it is a priority for the Institute to ensure that principles of mutual benefit and equity are embedded in these partnerships as it works towards a culture of

Who are Sanger's 'partners'?

The term 'partner' is used throughout this report, and may refer to individual researchers, research managers, administrative staff, research teams, or the research institutes in which these researchers, staff and teams are based. One, all, or a combination of these stakeholders may be relevant, depending on the context. Readers should consider who they are interacting with at each stage of the research pipeline when applying the principles set out in this report.

¹ <https://www.sanger.ac.uk/people/international-fellows/>

² <https://www.sanger.ac.uk/about/study/masters-programmes/>

research excellence.

1.2 Power, privilege and the importance of equity

When collaborating internationally, it is essential for research teams at the Sanger Institute to be aware of the privileges they will often have in comparison to their partners based in LMICs. These privileges may include access to large-scale genomic sequencing technology and physical or remote access to high-performance computing infrastructure, secure supply chains for biological reagents, stable funding, reliable power supply, opportunities for networking and training, and substantial administrative and technical support. Additionally, funders and research institutes in High-Income Countries (HICs) are often perceived as the primary funders and intellectual designers of global research, with researchers from LMICs typically viewed as collectors of samples and metadata or demographic data. This hierarchical perception can lead to the interests of partners based in LMICs being overlooked, exacerbating the power imbalance that already exists due to resource disparity. To address these longstanding inequalities in HIC-LMIC research collaborations, Sanger research teams must proactively recognise these imbalances in power and resources, and co-design strategies with their partners to mitigate and address them.

Use of 'LMIC' terminology

Using targeted categories like geographical areas is generally more precise and inclusive than using terms such as 'Low- and Middle-Income Country (LMIC)' or 'global south', which imply categorisation based on financial resource and potentially perpetuate a notion of 'otherness'. Despite this, the term 'LMIC' is used throughout this report because transparency in power and resource imbalances, and subsequent action to mitigate and address these imbalances, are central themes. Therefore, it is relevant in this case to highlight the income status of the country in which a partner is based.

It is important to adopt reflective practice before applying any such category or term, to ensure that the categorisation is relevant and the message for the intended audience is received correctly. Sanger researchers and staff should refer to the [GRL Inclusive Language Guide](#) for further support.

Failure to acknowledge and address these inequalities could mean that Sanger research teams that work in LMIC settings, or handle samples or data collected from LMICs, inadvertently exploit power imbalances through the practice of inequitable research that does not seek meaningful input from, or bring benefit to, local researchers

and communities – a practice often termed ‘parachute’ or ‘helicopter’ science. Not only is the disregard of benefit sharing exploitative, but if local partners are not meaningfully involved in the research, then critical skills and knowledge are overlooked – limiting problem-solving power and likely lowering the quality of research outputs. Furthermore, excluding local partners from decision-making processes from the outset risks setting a research agenda that is misaligned with regional and local priorities, thus lessening the impact and value of the research.

Therefore, it is both an ethical and scientific imperative that Sanger research teams avoid such practices and instead collaborate closely with partners based in LMICs in an equitable manner.

1.3 Methodology

The Sanger Institute’s Policy and Advocacy Team first explored literature and existing frameworks to identify initial principles of equitable research collaboration. We also held conversations with Sanger Faculty and operations staff to better understand existing policies and practices of international research.

Following this, we interviewed 21 experts based in countries of Europe, North America, South Asia, Africa, and Latin America. Interviewees had expertise and experience across genomics research, biomedical research, social science, bioethics, research funding, science policy, publishing, and community engagement. We discussed experiences and perspectives on equitable research collaboration and sought feedback on our initial principles of equitable collaboration.

Using these findings, we produced a draft report on equitable collaboration. This draft report comprised guidelines for Sanger research teams to collaborate equitably with partners based in LMICs. The draft was presented at two workshops to experts in biomedical science, science policy, public health, social science, sustainable biotechnology, bioinformatics capacity strengthening, bioethics, global partnerships, international education, research funding, and publishing. The workshops, hosted in collaboration with the Centre for Science and Policy (CSaP), prompted lively discussion and highlighted several aspects to consider, including the importance of:

- Taking time to build trust between partners
- Enabling intellectual co-leadership from start to end of the research project
- Aligning the research agenda with local priorities

- Ensuring mutual long-term benefit through sharing of research capacity, such as bioinformatics skills, sequencing technologies, computing infrastructure or access, grant writing skills, and administrative training.

We used the insights and feedback from the workshops, along with feedback from Sanger research teams and operations staff and external stakeholders, to guide the development of the report. See Annex A for a list of experts who contributed perspectives and feedback.

1.4 Outline and scope

This report aims to support the Sanger Institute and its research teams to collaborate with partners based in LMICs in an equitable manner. However, many of the principles can be applied to any kind of collaboration.

The document is divided into two sections:

- 1. A working definition of an equitable collaboration**
- 2. Guidelines for Sanger research teams to collaborate equitably with partners based in LMICs**

It is important to note that this document focuses solely on the roles of the Sanger Institute and its research teams, and the guidelines should **not** be imposed on collaborators. Rather, all partners may choose to use these guidelines as a basis for starting conversations on equity and should work together to address equity on a case-by-case basis.

The report is limited in scope to partnerships between the Sanger Institute and research institutes based in LMICs, as well as partnerships between respective research teams. However, principles of equity also need to be considered when Sanger research teams engage with any stakeholders outside of academia. This is particularly important when carrying out research with human participants or samples of cultural significance.

2. A working definition of an equitable collaboration

There is no perfect definition of an equitable collaboration, but we have chosen to adopt a working definition that captures some key principles:

‘a mutually advantageous partnership built on trust, where all partners are intellectual contributors to the project who work together to ensure that tasks and rewards are shared in a fair manner that addresses inequalities’.

This definition is comprised of several elements:

- **Striving for mutual benefit.** This requires a deep understanding of partners’ priorities and an awareness that goals and beneficial outcomes may look very different for each partner.
- **Trust.** For a collaboration to be successful, partners should have confidence that all involved are sincerely striving for mutual benefit.
- **Intellectual involvement.** All partners should be actively involved in decision-making throughout the research process from the earliest stages. This includes decisions on the research agenda, designing experiments and disseminating results.
- **Sharing tasks and rewards fairly.** Tasks, such as sample collection, sequencing, data analysis and manuscript preparation, and rewards, such as manuscript authorship and translation opportunities, should be shared between partners equitably. Note that an equitable partnership does not mean that the roles of all partners will be ‘the same’. In fact, roles will likely vary considerably due to the different types of skills and knowledge that each partner contributes, and the different priorities that each partner has.
- **Addressing inequalities.** All partners should have honest and transparent discussions to understand respective research barriers and privileges, and then decide how to move forwards in a way that, as far as possible, redistributes power in the short- and long-term. An equitable collaboration will often prioritise the co-design of capacity strengthening strategies to empower partners based in LMICs to lead on projects with reduced dependency on partners based in HICs in the long term.

3. Guidelines for Sanger research teams

To enable fair and effective collaboration, equity should be embedded throughout all stages of the research process, from partnership building through research design and execution to result dissemination. This section contains guidelines arranged chronologically throughout the research process to support Sanger research teams who collaborate, or wish to collaborate, with partners based at LMIC institutes.

These guidelines are divided into the following sections:

3.1 Establishing a trust-based partnership

3.2 Formalising a collaboration

3.3 Conducting a joint research project

3.4 Sharing and strengthening research capacity

3.5 Disseminating outputs and next steps

These guidelines are not a rigid checklist of instructions, but should rather serve as a suggested starting point towards a more detailed strategy for equitable collaboration. This strategy should be developed with partners on a case-by-case basis, and should be responsive to partners' priorities and perspectives on equity.

Sanger research teams – not only individual scientists

These guidelines are intended to support all individuals in a research team to embed equity into the research collaboration process. For this reason, the term 'Sanger research teams' is used instead of 'Sanger researchers' or 'Sanger scientists'.

It is not just the responsibility of the Group Leader to embed equitable principles within the collaboration, but everyone within the team. This includes PhDs and postdocs, who may be interacting with collaborators on a day-to-day basis, and research managers, who are integral to managing research projects and various collaboration processes.

3.1 Establishing a trust-based partnership

An equitable collaboration requires co-leadership and intellectual involvement from all partners, which can only be accomplished if principles of equity are incorporated from the beginning of the research project. This section provides advice for Sanger research teams commencing international research projects and explores ways to identify potential collaborators, begin building trust, and establish equitable research strategies.

Guideline 1A:

Consider varied approaches to identify potential collaborators based in LMICs, such as encouraging LMIC-based research teams to approach you with research ideas, performing landscape analyses, leveraging networks, and building on previous relationships.

Sanger research teams should use conference presentations or external-facing websites to encourage LMIC-based research teams to reach out with collaboration ideas. This approach avoids the more typical and less equitable scenario in which researchers based in HICs impose pre-designed research agendas on research teams based in LMICs.

Alternatively, Sanger research teams could identify local research teams with expertise in the relevant field to co-design the research question and agenda and to co-lead the project. New collaborators can be identified through analysing the publication landscape and leveraging existing networks. It should be noted that literature analysis might introduce biases in the search for potential partners, as the publication landscape is skewed towards Anglophone researchers and researchers based in LMICs have historically been excluded from lead authorship positions.

Another option is to reengage with previous collaborators. This can help build on a foundation of mutual trust established during previous projects, and the existing knowledge of a partner's priorities and research barriers can facilitate more effective co-design of equitable research strategies. Additionally, re-engaging with the same partners over multiple projects allows for long-term, sustainable sharing and strengthening of research capacity.

Note that the choice of collaborator should primarily be based on the expertise needed to perform the research, but it is also important to consider how equity may be more easily achieved if the research teams share compatible working styles, ethical values, and long-term goals.

Guideline 1B:

Prioritise building trust with potential partners through transparency, receptive communication and active listening, and by emphasising the personal importance of research equity.

After identifying or resuming a partnership with a research team based in an LMIC, Sanger research teams should prioritise mutual trust building. Earning trust is a gradual, long-term process that all partners can facilitate through transparency, receptive communication and active listening. Sanger research teams can begin to demonstrate trustworthiness by acknowledging the personal importance of research equity, perhaps by sharing and endorsing the guidelines set out here or by providing examples of equitable strategies used in previous collaborations.

Guideline 1C:

Before entering into a formal collaboration, jointly agree on a research agenda and co-develop research and equity-oriented strategies with potential partners. Consider meeting in-person to understand local contexts to help with this.

Before formalising a collaboration, all potential partners should jointly define a research question and agenda. All potential partners should play an active role in this process so that the agenda reflects the priorities of all and pays attention to the needs of the local region in which the research takes place. Following this, all aspects of the research process, from applying for a grant to dissemination of anticipated research outputs, should be planned out with the involvement of all potential partners. Put plans in place to ensure that LMIC-based partners take (joint) leadership roles throughout research design, sample and data collection, data analysis and result delivery to, in turn, enable joint lead authorship of research outputs.

In addition to research plans, all potential partners should discuss and co-design equity-oriented goals and strategies that account for respective research barriers and enablers. Equity-oriented goals may relate to inclusivity in decision-making, recognition of contributions, sharing of benefits, maintenance and accessibility of resources and

datasets, translation of knowledge into local benefit, sharing of revenue and downstream health and economic benefits arising from intellectual property, and strengthening of research capacity. Research capacity strengthening should be a priority; however, it can be time-consuming, challenging and costly, and so Sanger research teams should draw on institutional support and be honest with potential partners from the outset about the extent they can contribute. Sanger research teams could share their principles of equity (e.g. the guidelines of this document, or their own views) with potential partners to aid the design of these goals and strategies, but they should avoid imposing these principles on potential partners, and instead explicitly ask potential partners what they think an equitable outcome looks like.

Time and workload should be allocated fairly in research and equity-oriented strategies, factoring in extra time for equitable establishment of the collaboration, especially at the funding and contract negotiation stage. In addition, all potential partners should consider meeting in-person and locally, keeping in mind the investment required by local research teams or communities to host such visits. These visits may enable the Sanger research team, and Sanger support staff, to better understand local priorities and contexts, interact with the wider research teams, and experience the

Case Study

Project JAGUAR – Distribution of roles

Project JAGUAR is a collaborative research project funded by the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative that aims to map the diversity of immune cells across previously understudied populations across Latin America, looking particularly at the effect of genetic ancestries on the composition and gene expression regulation of immune cells. This research could improve our understanding of why people manifest different diseases and why certain immune conditions are more prevalent in certain regions.

The project is co-led by research teams across Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Mexico, Peru, Uruguay and the UK. The research teams in Latin America are leading on participant recruitment and sample collection, with Sanger leading on genomic data generation. All partners work together to analyse the data and produce and share the results of the research.

Importantly, a decision was made at the project outset to not request funds for analytical postdocs based at Sanger, but instead to distribute data analysis roles with analytical leads in the Latin American research teams. Although this brought some extra logistical challenges, this approach is enabling Latin American partners to contribute more fully to the research process as well as supporting expertise and capacity to be built in partner institutes.

cultural, ethical, political and regulatory context of the potential collaborator's setting. For example, it is important for Sanger research teams to understand local challenges around supply chains for reagents and equipment before planning experiments. Partners should develop strategies to adapt to or overcome these challenges and contexts.

3.2 Formalising a collaboration

After co-developing a research agenda and research and equity-oriented strategies, the collaboration will need to be formalised. When doing so, Sanger research teams should endeavour to minimise any inequities stemming from funding imbalances and contract negotiation processes. This section contains advice on applying for funding, fairly negotiating research contracts and co-designing principles of partnership.

Guideline 2A:

Submit a joint grant proposal that incorporates capacity strengthening needs when applying for third party funding. In all cases, decide jointly with partners how to allocate funding in an equitable manner.

When applying for third party funding, all partners should submit a joint grant proposal where local Group Leaders may be considered main or joint principal investigators on the grant. The proposal should be based on an agreed research agenda that responds to specific local research needs and allows for joint intellectual leadership. Partners should identify funding sources that cover capacity strengthening needs, including costs of bidirectional travel, and that can support equitable practices, such as salaries of experts in community engagement, experts in local research regulation and ethics, and translators, if applicable. It should be ensured that any funding requirements are acceptable and beneficial for all partners.

Formal ethics approval may be required as part of the grant application process. If appropriate, partners should seek ethics approval from all partner countries, and ensure the research proposal aligns with local ethical principles. If seeking ethics approval from multiple countries is not appropriate then the reasons for this should be made transparent in discussions among partners. Note that pre- and post-funding procedures such as due diligence and ethics approval may take considerable time. Allowance for these procedures should be made from the start when co-designing research strategies.

Much of the Sanger Institute's research is funded from a core grant from Wellcome, so in many cases the Sanger Institute may contribute all of the project funding and award sub-grants to collaborator institutes. Although this situation may risk exacerbating power imbalance, it can also bring a degree of security and predictability to the collaboration, thereby facilitating equity. Hybrid approaches are also possible: collaborators might rely on Sanger's core grant for initial projects, but then apply for joint third party grants for further research. No matter the funding arrangement, all partners should contribute to decisions on how the money is spent, with consideration of how to allocate the funding in an equitable manner that ensures long-term mutual benefit and takes into account the planned division of work. Sanger research teams should provide support and time for LMIC-based partners to appropriately budget research in a way that accounts for indirect research costs.

Guideline 2B:

Agree on important high-level components of the collaboration arrangement with research partners in advance of formal legal negotiation. After negotiation, check with partners that research agreements contain mutually beneficial terms.

Upon formally entering a research partnership, research contracts will be negotiated with partners. These contracts may include Memorandum of Agreements (MoA), Research Collaboration Agreements (RCA) and/or Material Transfer Agreements (MTA). These agreements often include legally-binding arrangements around 'ownership' and sharing of ideas, samples and data, commercialisation opportunities, expected roles, authorship of publications, and research capacity strengthening. It might be useful for the research teams to agree on high-level components of the collaboration arrangement before formal negotiation takes place between institute legal teams. Contracts may need to be translated, and any disagreements should be resolved together, with involvement of the research teams and administrative staff of the partner institutes.

Before signing these contracts, Sanger research teams should check with partners that the terms are beneficial for all and that concerns and priorities have been sufficiently considered, especially if partners have limited legal support. In particular, terms on ownership of outputs, intellectual property rights and associated copyright or patent matters should account for the contributions of all individuals leading to a research output. In addition, all partners should formally agree when commercially relevant or sensitive data and findings derived from the project can be made publicly available.

Guideline 2C:

Agree on a set of simple-language, non-legally binding 'guiding principles of partnership' with all partners – including junior researchers.

The formal collaboration contracts set out some basic terms for a research partnership. These terms may suffice, or partners might want to develop an additional simple-language, non-legal document that sets out expectations in more detail, i.e. 'guiding principles of partnership', possibly adding these as an Annex to the legal collaboration contract. Such an approach has the advantage that all partners, including junior researchers, can more easily contribute to its co-design.

Such principles should avoid legal jargon and could include agreements on respective roles, behavioural expectations, frequency of meetings, project timeframes, approaches to regulatory and ethical compliance, publication and authorship expectations, capacity strengthening strategies, and translation possibilities. The principles may also include decisions on how to apportion credit, clarification on ensuring equitable external representation of the project, and references to policies on access, sharing and stewardship of research resources, samples and data. For large research consortia, these principles of partnership could establish whose voices are represented in decision-making panels and governance committees to ensure that all partners can effectively participate.

All partners should recognise the importance of inclusivity and equity.

Case Study

Global Pneumococcal Sequencing (GPS) Project – Collaboration and Publication Guidelines

Funded by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation and Wellcome, [the GPS Project](#) aims to establish a worldwide genomic surveillance network of *Streptococcus pneumoniae* to provide evidence for pneumococcal disease control. The project is led by Prof Stephen Bentley at the Wellcome Sanger Institute and Dr Lesley McGee at the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention and includes over 50 project partners from all regions of the world. By the end of 2019, almost 100 scientists had contributed to the sequencing of over 26,000 pneumococcal bacterial isolates from over 50 countries.

The GPS team created a set of 'Collaboration and Publication guidelines' to ensure fair and transparent procedures and appropriate recognition and benefit for all partners. These include guidance on DNA sequence data deposition, data release to partners, secondary use of data in sub-studies, and publication and authorship of manuscripts and conference abstracts.

Although principles of partnership are not legally binding, ensuring that they are co-designed and agreed by all partners – including junior members – means that they can be referenced throughout the collaboration and used to hold partners to account. A procedure for reporting and investigating incidents of parties breaking their commitments should be clarified at this stage.

3.3 Conducting a joint research project

Equity should be considered throughout the implementation of the research project, with all partners working to overcome practical challenges through frequent communication, transparency, and mutual respect. This section contains guidance on communicating with partners, evaluating progress, and valuing cultural differences.

Guideline 3A:

Hold regular meetings with partners to exchange updates on research progress and develop inclusive strategies for overcoming obstacles, making sure to share meeting notes among all team members. Consider using online collaboration platforms between meetings.

All partners should connect at regular intervals agreed at the start of the collaboration, ideally by video call or in-person meetings. Recognise that cultural and language differences may impact communication, and strive to ensure that decision-making is inclusive. To allow all partners to fully prepare for meetings, agendas should be provided in advance to enable full participation, especially if there are language barriers. Key decisions should be jointly determined and communicated, research methods and results shared, and progress against agreed research objectives evaluated, adapting timelines if needed. All partners should listen to and learn from one another to better understand obstacles to research progress and develop strategies to circumvent or mitigate these.

Methods should be established for updating those absent from meetings, for example by sharing meeting notes and updates to a shared cloud drive. These records should be available to all members of respective research teams, where appropriate, including administrative and technical staff and junior members, and there should be ways for these members to share queries or comments. Consider online collaboration platforms such as Slack or Confluence to maintain communication between meetings.

Guideline 3B:

Regularly evaluate progress against equity-oriented goals for research collaboration, particularly those relating to research capacity strengthening, and ensure routes for raising concerns are established and maintained.

All partners should use these regular meetings to evaluate progress against equity-oriented goals set at the start of the collaboration. All partners should be supported to freely express their opinions on progress without fear of negative consequences, and clear, straightforward procedures for raising concerns about inequitable practices should be maintained throughout. In particular, seek feedback from partners on the collaboration's impact on research capacity strengthening.

Guideline 3C:

Agree on behavioural expectations and foster an inclusive working environment where all are encouraged to voice ideas, priorities and concerns. Support and celebrate linguistic and cultural diversity.

With reference to behavioural guidelines of the respective partner institutes, e.g. the [GRL Behavioural Competency Framework \(BCF\)](#), all partners should agree on behavioural expectations at the outset of the collaboration. All partners should aim to create and maintain a culture where everyone is encouraged to voice their concerns, ideas and priorities without fear of reprisal. All partners should acknowledge and show appreciation for each other's skills, effort and expertise brought to the research project.

Cultural differences lead to a wide range of perspectives and knowledge sources that can improve problem-solving power, and thus add value to the collaboration. However, these differences can also present difficulties if mishandled. Misunderstandings can arise if partners fail to understand one another's perspectives or communicate in different ways, especially if a collaboration consists of a complex multiplicity of individuals with different cultural backgrounds. Clear strategies should be established from the outset to support understanding of the cultural and ethical values of the local settings that collaborators are based in, and difficulties should be addressed through compassionate and candid communication, with researchers willing to adapt working practices accordingly.

Language barriers can disadvantage those who do not use English as their first language, particularly during discussions of research strategies and negotiation of contracts. In such circumstances, ensure that all partners have the opportunity and time

they need to present their views and are able to use communication platforms that work best for them. Seek translation support if necessary.

3.4 Sharing and strengthening research capacity

The sharing and strengthening of research capacity enables all partners to shape, lead and sustain research in the long-term with reduced dependency on external stakeholders, and provides HIC-based scientists with the means to better understand and navigate the wider context of international research. Furthermore, the enhancement of research capacity will support research into challenging global issues, including health inequalities, infectious disease and biodiversity loss. This section contains guidance on capacity sharing and strengthening at the researcher and institute levels. Readers should keep in mind that exchange of knowledge and skills should be a reciprocal process.

Guideline 4A:

In a sustainable and holistic manner, share skills and knowledge, support broader professional development, and create efficiencies in the research process.

Research teams at the Sanger Institute can play a major role in strengthening partners' research capacity through the provision of training and broader professional support. In addition, LMIC-based partners may be well placed to strengthen the Sanger research team's capacity in terms of field-related expertise, provide understanding of local political, cultural, regulatory and ethical contexts, and offer innovative insights in social science and responsible research. All partners should work together to determine the types of capacity strengthening initiatives that should be prioritised, and strategies for achieving these. Ideally, a portion of funding for the research project should have been set aside for capacity strengthening activities.

A key way to strengthen capacity is skills training. This could include training in sequencing methodologies, storage, access and sharing of genetic data, cloud computing for data storage and analysis, bioinformatics, and statistics.

LMIC-based partners should be financially supported to visit Sanger to build relationships and develop specific technical skills that they can then share with colleagues upon return to their home institution. Sanger research teams could also consider collaborating with the Global Training team at Wellcome Connecting Science to develop locally delivered training courses.

Sustainability of skills is key to capacity strengthening. Where possible, a ‘train the trainer’ approach should be adopted to provide partners with the tools to subsequently train colleagues in the long term. Another way to facilitate sustainability is through sharing protocols for sampling and laboratory procedures, software tools, and training materials for coding and data analysis on freely accessible online platforms as part of Sanger’s commitment to open science.

In all cases, training should be co-developed with partners to ensure courses are useful, targeted at the appropriate technical level, and contain relevant test datasets. Resources should take into account and be adaptable to local contexts.

Mentorship can also be an effective method for facilitating academic independence and supporting career advancement, particularly for early career researchers who may not be familiar with funders’ expectations for proposals. Mentorship could involve offering guidance on grant applications, reporting, manuscript preparation, writing masters or PhD theses, presenting at conferences, navigating the publication process, ethics and governance processes, leadership, confidence and communication, building networks and a professional social media presence – though it is important to be mindful of different practices and expectations in different global settings. As individuals from both Sanger and partner institutes will have much to learn from one another, mentorship

Case Study

Global Pneumococcal Sequencing (GPS) Project – Capacity development

The GPS Project aims to develop [sustainable genomic surveillance capacity](#) by supporting the decentralisation of data generation and analysis. The GPS team engaged with partners from 10 institutes in 8 LMIC countries to discuss the feasibility of local data generation and what resources are required. Using this information, the GPS Project is supporting skills training for local researchers to become independent analysers of genomic data through online training, in-person workshops, and the sharing of online resources. In 2019, the GPS team and collaborators from six LMIC countries came together for a week of training focused on the analysis and drafting of country-specific genomic analysis papers for publication, some of which have been published. The GPS Project has also supported one-to-one hands-on training and mentorship in genomics analysis for early-career researchers.

should be a two-way process. In addition, reverse mentorship, where junior researchers mentor senior colleagues, can be an effective method for junior partners to share their experiences, challenges and the barriers that they encounter, thereby driving change.

Researchers should be aware that providing training in isolated techniques is of limited benefit. Rather, holistic training in processes across the research pipeline is more effective for long-term sustainability, e.g. training in how to produce or obtain materials and reagents alongside training in sequencing techniques and bioinformatics analyses, and writing grants and research papers.

While long-term sustainability should be prioritised, Sanger research teams may also consider using their resources to help partners overcome short-term practical obstacles, as improving efficiency in the research process is beneficial to all stakeholders. Partners should together identify logistical issues and decide how resources could be used equitably to overcome these (e.g. purchasing and posting reagents and equipment).

Case Study

Wellcome Connecting Science – Global training

A number of Wellcome Sanger Institute and LMIC-based scientists support Wellcome Connecting Science in delivering [global training courses](#). These courses adopt a train-the-trainer approach to support sustainable knowledge transfer and many take place virtually or in global regions in collaboration with local partners. For example, in summer 2023 Wellcome Connecting Science organised a [workshop on Single Cell Genomics](#) for scientists working across Latin American countries and the Caribbean islands. This course comprised training in hands-on laboratory and computational bioinformatics, as well as networking opportunities and cultivation of a community of practice. Course instructors included experts from Latin America, North America, and the UK. Wellcome Connecting Science have also carried out bioinformatics training courses in [distributed classroom formats](#) to reach over 300 participants and 22 countries in Africa, Asia and Latin America.

Case Study

The Genomic Surveillance Unit (GSU)

The [Genomic Surveillance Unit \(GSU\)](#) was launched by the Wellcome Sanger Institute in collaboration with UK Health Security Agency. The aim of the GSU is to support partners around the world, including those based in LMICs, to build capacity in genomic surveillance to enable local infectious disease control and pandemic preparedness.

The GSU develops, runs, supports and maintains open products that enable the genomic surveillance needs of partners to be met. These products support all parts of the genomic surveillance pipeline, including sample collection, high-throughput genome sequencing, data analysis and delivery of information to guide public health, and are designed to be applicable to a range of different diseases. The GSU also provides guidance and training to support partners to establish sustainable surveillance programmes.

The GSU partners with research institutes through activities supported by research grants, and with national public health agencies who can provide sustainable in-country funding. In all cases, the GSU works closely with partners worldwide to learn lessons from those familiar with local settings to enable the delivery of services and products that are locally-relevant, low-cost and easy to implement.

Case Study

The Centre for Genomic Pathogen Surveillance (CGPS) – Good Financial Practice Grant (GFPG)

The Centre for Genomic Pathogen Surveillance (CGPS), which was based jointly at the Oxford Big Data Institute and the Wellcome Sanger Institute until 2021, supported the Central Research Laboratory at Kempegowda Institute of Medical Sciences (CRL KIMS), India, to be certified under the [Good Financial Grant Practice \(GFPG\)](#) international standard in June 2020. The GFPG is the world's first international standard for the financial governance and management of grant funding. It was developed by the African Academy of Sciences and organisations can use the GFPG certification to reduce power imbalance in financial due diligence checks. The process to GFPG certification supported the development of CRL KIMS's operational and grant management capacity and will enhance its ability to attract and manage international funding.

Guideline 4B:

Work with partners to identify and overcome limitations in institutional and infrastructural capacity that pose significant barriers to research.

As well as capacity of research teams, it is important to consider the capacity of the wider research ecosystem in which scientists operate. In particular, limitations in institutional capacity (e.g. administrative, legal, research governance, procurement and financial support) and infrastructural capacity (e.g. laboratories and equipment, reliable power supply and internet connectivity) might present significant barriers for partners based in LMICs.

There are limits to how much Sanger research teams can help in this area, but they should strategize with partners to overcome these hurdles where possible. For example, the Sanger research team, with the support of the Sanger Institute, might be able to provide sequencing equipment or access to cloud computing servers to collect, store and analyse large-scale data.

In addition, the Sanger Institute may be able to help develop institutional capacity in finance, legal, research governance and administration to enable institutions to more effectively conduct research, write and transparently administer grants, navigate ethical review and compliance procedures, and negotiate fair contracts. The adoption of the Good Financial Grant Practice (GFGP) certification by partner institutes is an example of how research organisations can support developing capacity in this manner^{3,4}.

Guideline 4C:

Adapt roles and responsibilities throughout the research process to allow partners to take advantage of strengthened research capacity.

Partners should be entrusted to take ownership of their strengthened research capacity. All partners should together decide how tasks and leadership roles should be transferred between institutes and/or research teams, and the mechanisms of doing so.

For example, sequencing and bioinformatics analyses might initially be performed predominantly by the Sanger research team, but as sustainable skills and technology capacity is shared with LMIC-based partners, LMIC-based partners might take the lead on relevant areas of project operation, as well as take on new research. As the

³ <https://www.bdi.ox.ac.uk/news/world2019s-first-good-financial-grant-practice-gfgp-certification>

⁴ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8634540/>

leadership roles for a project shifts, authorship positioning on research outputs must be adapted accordingly.

3.5 Disseminating outputs and next steps

After collecting and analysing data and producing research outputs, partners should share their data and outputs with the scientific and wider communities in an appropriate manner. If possible, partners should also look to the future and endeavour to sustain their partnership beyond the initial research project. This section contains guidance on acknowledging contributions, ensuring equitable benefit-sharing, sharing data, disseminating results, and ensuring long-term sustainability of the research relationship.

Guideline 5A:

Ensure that all partners receive the recognition and rewards agreed upon at the outset of the collaboration, such as publication authorship, credit in press releases, opportunities to present externally, and shares of revenue and downstream benefits from commercialisation of intellectual property.

All partners should seek mutual benefit, ensuring that all input to the research project is valued and rewarded. All partners should be able to intellectually contribute throughout the duration of the project and then be appropriately recognised and acknowledged in research outputs. Recognition may include joint lead authorship of scientific publications, credit in press releases, and opportunities to present through scientific conferences and media channels. All members of the research teams who contributed intellectually, not merely the principal investigators from each centre, must be named as authors in research outputs. Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) may be useful in acknowledging the role played by each individual collaborator⁵. All partners should be keenly aware of the importance of authorship for the career advancement of early career researchers in particular. All partners should decide together which journal to publish research results in, acknowledging that publishing in multidisciplinary internationally renowned journals may be beneficial for career advancement, but publishing in more specialised or locally relevant journals may lead to more direct health or policy impact. One option may be to publish initially in international journals, and then also support LMIC-based partners to share results in local news articles, blogs or TV or radio broadcasts, which are likely to have a greater reach to local communities

⁵ <https://credit.niso.org/>

and key local stakeholders.

If opportunities for patenting and commercialisation of intellectual property arise, all partners and, if applicable, research participants and other relevant stakeholders, should be involved in discussions to ensure that all are able to share equitably in any revenue that is generated. If applicable, thought should also be given to how all partners might equitably receive indirect downstream health and economic benefits, such as access to medical products and the creation of spin-out companies and local jobs.

Guideline 5B:

If it is possible and secure to do so, share data between partners throughout the project life cycle. Ensure open (or managed) access to data and publications, but consider ways to address fears of scooping.

Along with decisions on publications and intellectual property, decisions on data sharing should also reflect equitable principles. If it is possible and secure to do so, data should be shared with collaborators throughout the project life cycle, in accordance with timelines and plans agreed at the outset of the collaboration. Data should not be stored locally at the Sanger Institute exclusively if partners are not able to access it, unless this cannot be avoided and partners are satisfied with this arrangement.

The Sanger Institute mandates deposition of data in open access repositories as well as open access publishing – subject to some exceptions – due to the myriad benefits this brings, such as increased reach and impact of research methods and results, facilitation of further collaboration, and improved research reproducibility and integrity. However, if there are concerns regarding open access data, measures could be considered that allow for external sharing of data whilst recognising these concerns. These measures could include implementing a short delay before releasing data, in line with Sanger’s Data Sharing Policy⁶, to provide partners with confidence that they will be able to analyse data and publish results before competitors can.

Guideline 5C:

Maintain sustainable relationships with partners after the initial research project has finished by keeping in touch and actively seeking further collaboration opportunities.

Sanger research teams should consider maintaining contact with partners after the

⁶ <https://www.sanger.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/Data-Sharing-Policy-and-Guidelines-March-2023.pdf>

research project concludes through calls or in-person catch-ups, and continue to share ideas or provide support as needed. This could include helping with identification of funding and publication opportunities, or providing assistance with grant applications and data analysis. To facilitate new partnerships, the Sanger research team could offer to connect partners with their broader scientific network and, with permission, add

Case Study

A retreat to increase microbiome research in underrepresented populations

As with other genomics fields, human microbiome research has historically been dominated by studies of European and North-American populations. To address this imbalance, Dr Hilary Browne and Dr Majdi Osman in Sanger's Host-Microbiota Interactions lab (led by Dr. Trevor Lawley) with co-organisers in Kenya and Pakistan held a two-day retreat at the Wellcome Genome Campus in April 2023. The main aim of the retreat was to discuss how to accelerate microbiome research for the improvement of child health in Asian, Latin American and African countries. Supported by Wellcome Connecting Science and the Gates foundation, the retreat brought together 40 researchers, funders and industry representatives from over 20 countries.

During the retreat, participants presented their research and shared perspectives on the opportunities to accelerate microbiome research in LMICs. Key proposals included the training of early-career researchers across different laboratory and computational techniques, supplemented with mentoring and career development support. In addition, participants were of the view that laboratory infrastructure gaps need to be addressed, including supply chain constraints and the high costs of reagents. Participants also felt there should be more funding opportunities targeted at researchers based in LMICs, especially early-career researchers, and that collaboration based on mutual trust that brings together expertise in different areas will continue to be essential going forward.

Following the retreat, the organisers have written a [Nature Comment piece](#) to outline ways to increase microbiome research in children in underrepresented populations. Longer-term, the Gates Foundation have agreed to fund travel grants to up to 10 early career researchers based in LMICs to enable them to spend one to two months in another research lab to learn microbiome techniques. This reflects a key take-home message from the retreat that skills training and establishment of collaborative networks can significantly accelerate the professional development of early career researchers.

details of the collaboration to the Sanger Institute's website to boost visibility⁷.

All partners should seek further ways to collaborate formally, as extending partnerships into the long-term allows for further building of mutual trust and facilitates more sustainable capacity strengthening. Further collaboration opportunities might arise from downstream projects involving the reanalysis of datasets that were collected during the initial research project, considering that genomics involves 'big data', where a single dataset may be used to answer a plethora of different research questions. Sanger research teams should support partners to lead on downstream projects that respond to specific local research needs.

⁷ <https://www.sanger.ac.uk/science/collaborations/>

4. Conclusion

A collaborative research ecosystem that is equitable and brings mutual benefit to all involved will lead to science that is more impactful and inclusive of different knowledge sources. Such an ecosystem requires all research stakeholders, including individual researchers and research managers, research institutes, funding organisations and publishers, to be conscious of power and resource imbalances in research partnerships and take action to account for and mitigate these.

This report has outlined some principles of equitable collaboration that the Sanger Institute could adopt to play its role in building a more equitable international research ecosystem. We outline guidelines for Sanger research teams to consider equity throughout the research collaboration process, from setting up a collaboration through to disseminating results. These principles should be seen as a suggested baseline that individual research and operations teams can build upon with partners on a case-by-case basis. The principles should be adaptable in response to feedback from partners.

The focus of this report has been partnerships between the Sanger Institute and research institutes based in LMICs, as well as partnerships between respective research teams. However, principles of equity also need to be considered when Sanger research teams engage with any stakeholders including academics, public groups, patients, clinicians, local leaders, community workers, and policy makers. This is particularly important when carrying out research with human participants or samples of cultural significance. Although the principles set out in this report may be applied to some aspects of wider engagement, Sanger research teams should find more specific resources and expertise to support them to work equitably with stakeholders outside of academia.

For readers interested in learning more about equitable collaboration, relevant literature and resources can be found in Annex B.

Annex A: Stakeholder engagement and acknowledgement

The Sanger Policy and Advocacy Team is hugely grateful to the internal and external experts who shared their experiences, expertise and feedback through interview, email, and/or workshop participation. Note that experts were not asked to endorse the report or its findings and they contributed in a personal capacity, not on behalf of their affiliated organisations. Please see below for a list of external experts who have given permission to be acknowledged.

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Annex B: Further resources

Resources

- UKCDR & Essence Equitable Partnerships Resource Hub - <https://www.ukcdr.org.uk/guidance/equitable-partnerships-hub/>
- The Cape Town Statement on Fostering Research Integrity through Fairness and Equity - <https://www.wcrif.org/guidance/cape-town-statement>
- UKCDR & Essence Four Approaches to Supporting Equitable Research Partnerships - <https://www.ukcdr.org.uk/resource/ukcdr-and-essence-2022-four-approaches-to-supporting-equitable-research-partnerships/>
- The Trust Code. A global code of conduct for equitable research partnerships - <https://www.globalcodeofconduct.org/>
- ACU Equitable Research Partnerships Toolkit - <https://www.acu.ac.uk/our-work/projects-and-programmes/equitable-research-partnerships-toolkit/>
- Essence: Five Keys to improving research costing in low- and middle-income countries - <https://tdr.who.int/publications/m/item/2012-05-11-five-keys-to-improving-research-costing-in-low-and-middle-income-countries>
- COHRED research fairness initiative - <https://rfi.cohred.org/>
- Rethinking Research Collaborative - <https://rethinkingresearchcollaborative.com/>
- Montreal Statement on Research Integrity in Cross-Boundary Research Collaborations - <https://www.wcrif.org/guidance/montreal-statement>
- Swiss Commission for Research Partnership with Developing Countries, KFPE: Guidelines for Research in Partnership with Developing Countries - https://www.zef.de/fileadmin/webfiles/downloads/conferences/VW_WS_Swiss_Guidelines.pdf
- CIOMS/WHO: International Ethical Guidelines for Health-related Research Involving Humans - <https://cioms.ch/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/WEB-CIOMS-EthicalGuidelines.pdf>
- EquiPar tool - <https://www.lshtm.ac.uk/research/centres-projects-groups/equipar-pilot-evaluation>

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